

A handbook

Fostering edible cities and landscapes with ***mundraub***

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1. Edible cities and landscapes

Get involved

In the past years we were happy to learn that our mundraub community successively added fruit trees to the mundraub map and created events and groups all around Germany and beyond. They all live by the mundraub philosophy and keep on spreading it. At the same time, while working with companies and municipalities as well as in different projects, we notice that the idea of edible landscapes and urban agriculture established more and more. Thus, the mundraub idea developed further.

But what exactly is the idea of mundraub? We want to transform cities and municipalities to edible places that can be experienced digitally and practically. The transfer of knowledge and guidelines as well as the networking with others intend to support people like you to capture and discover cities as edible, shapable and worth living in.

Delicious plants are able to grow in cities as well and they are just waiting to be noticed. They offer places that lust for attention and maybe even to be revalued as site for fruit trees or a *Benjes hedge* for birds and insects.

This handbook offers different possibilities for you to get involved in rediscovering the city and thinking it further: by organizing a mundraub tour, a harvesting event, a school trip, a team event, a birthday or by embedding the mundraub map in your blog or website.

Live by the mundraub philosophy and get involved!

Edible cities and landscapes

Edible cities and landscapes are, in the truest sense, on everyone's lips. More than ten years ago some people in Kassel (Germany) and Todmorden (England) were looking for an idea to make their city worth to live in and to create a place beyond a common language and culture. The edible city was the perfect epitome of that idea and so they took action: initiatives like the association "Essbare Stadt e.V." in Kassel or the network "Incredible Edible Todmorden" grew into established organisations. In the past years they inspired many people to join the idea of the edible city by building herb gardens and planting fruit trees and bushes. They found fellow campaigners among neighbours as well as local institutions. The idea of edible cities developed from an alleged crazy guerilla campaign into a real concept that was even taken into account when it came to urban planning as well as local planning for green spaces. By now it is put into practice by several cities and municipalities.

But why do cities aspire to be or become edible? Scientific studies show concrete positive impacts for cities and their residents to engage in urban agriculture (cf. Russo et al. 2017). Building roof gardens, cultivating tree pits in front of one's own house, collaborating in community gardens - those activities contribute to a better quality of life in cities and a higher level of satisfaction and local identification with one's own city. The project encourages people to come together, defying cultural, linguistic and age boundaries. They learn from each other and get to know and value nature while being at events together.

People who gain practical experience in nature are able to develop a sense of its value and need for protection. They can identify with a place they made a contribution to (cf. Petersen 2016). To collectively cultivate common properties creates a feeling of active solidarity. Furthermore people experience the sowing and harvesting of fresh

fruit and vegetables in urban spaces. Thus they take a stand against long routes of transportation and against the waste of precious food in supermarkets. No theoretical school lesson could ever teach more about nature than nature itself: it's great fun for children on a schooltrip to play nature memory, learning more about orchards and their more than 5.000 different animals and plants.

Networking can be rewarding for all players involved. As part of the project EdibleCitiesNetwork funded by the European Horizon2020 (duration: 2018-2023), mundraub makes important contributions to theoretical and practical solutions for edible cities.

Cities and mayors, too, have the opportunity to get involved. Since 2010 the city of Andernach promotes the slogan "Picking allowed instead of no trespassing". The Edible City of Andernach is continually developed further and remains at the center of media interest (cf. Kosack 2016).

mundraub co-developed the so-called "mundraub region Hasetal" that was based on edible green: after proposing and implementing an edible strategy in 2014, the project won the German Tourism Prize.

2. mundraub connects

The platform mundraub.org began with the simple idea of mapping locations of fruit trees, bushes and herbs, thus making them visible to others. It is now the world's biggest online platform that focuses on discovering and using edible landscapes, counting over 70.000 registered users and more than 50.000 fruity POIs.

Under the umbrella of the non-profit company Terra Concordia gGmbH mundraub also does think outside the digital box and carries out real-life projects regarding fruit: planting and harvesting events, guided tours through the edible city green as well as orchard days with classes from schools nearby. Besides partnering with municipalities and companies we are also an integral part of joint research projects. mundraub raises awareness of the social, economic and ecological significance of edible nature, locally grown and seasonal fruit. We inspire people to appreciate, use and sustainably consume our existing resources. In discovering and furthering reality through a digital medium, curiosity is sparked among target audiences not affined to nature, too. Thus, mundraub connects.

3. Who this book is for

This handbook is for all the people that can identify with the mundraub idea and want to use and spread it in the context of their own activity and impact:

- municipalities and cities
- organisations, initiatives and associations dedicated to the edible city
- companies
- administrations
- schools
- youth clubs
- committed individuals

We offer guidelines based on our knowledge and longtime experiences as part of the edible movement. There are no standards regarding the contents of an orchard day or the length of a mundraub tour. Certain decisions depend on certain aspects and circumstances that can't all be considered in this book. Thus you should adapt, when necessary, leave some things out or add new ones. The framework is the mundraub idea, the content is versatile. This handbook is a work in process. This can continuously lead to extensions and additions - by means of our own experience, but of your contribution as well.

We are looking forward to your feedback on this handbook via e-mail to info@mundraub.org.

4. Ingredients of an edible city

In the past years we developed several event formats that proved themselves in various campaigns and cooperations. We will present some of those in this chapter. They should be seen as modules that can be adapted and combined. Be Creative!

We want to inspire you to make ideas visible and to find ways to turn those ideas into reality. The important thing is: you are not alone! Divide the tasks. you don't have to and you can't do everything by yourself.

For the sake of nature and trees, we recommend you to consult experts depending on the event. Especially tree planting (▶ [chapter 4.1](#)) or tree pruning (▶ [chapter 4.5](#)) request professional instructions. Seek professional as well as pedagogical expertise to help you with the organisation and execution of events.

Do your research in relevant literature, watch video tutorials, take classes or go to workshops to learn all things necessary. The [mundraub event website](#) is one possibility to look for classes and workshops. Other options are continuing education centres or associations like [NABU](#), [BUND](#), [Grüne Liga](#), [Pomologen-Verein](#) or [Streuobstpädagogen](#). That way, it's also possible to find other people to help you in your endeavour.

The internet also offers you information by official institutions, i.e.

ministries. The **Federal Ministry for the Environment**, for example, offers a publication regarding Biodiversity for students and the accompanying booklet with further information for professors (in German; other publications are available in English as well).

Think about the importance of time management. There are lots of things to do before, during and after an event. Good organisation is essential.

Always pay attention to the **mundraub** rules (▶ **chapter 7.1**) and make sure, that all participants are aware of their responsibility towards wildlife and humans, respectively.

- ▶ mundraub.org/community/events
- ▶ nabu.de
- ▶ bund.net
- ▶ grueneliga.de
- ▶ pomologen-verein.de
- ▶ streuobst-paedagogen.de
- ▶ bmu.de/themen/bildung-beteiligung/bildungsservice

4.1 Planting fruit trees

Preparation and organisation

There are some important aspects to think about before planting a fruit tree: in case you have never planted a tree in your life, inform yourself about this subject matter! It's not rocket science, but nevertheless, it should be done correctly. Take part in planting workshops or improve your knowledge by reading appropriate technical literature. Many tree nurseries or environmental protection organisations uploaded video tutorials and **instructions** regarding this topic.

Be prepared to answer participant questions. If necessary, consult an expert for support.

Planting a tree is not for free. You will need to cover the costs, notably for trees and planting material (▶ [page 17](#)). Some possible sources of finance are:

- sponsors
- donations
- [foundations](#)
- crowdfunding
- self-financing

Think about a method that suits your needs. Are you going to plant two roadside trees in your district or an orchard with fifteen trees in the next village. Are you going to do a single planting or do you need money for several plantings?

A fundamental aspect to think about in advance, is a concept for the ongoing tree care, i.e. watering during hot seasons, tree pruning. Will it be your responsibility? Is there an agreement with the responsible authorities? Are you going to assign sponsorships for every tree? "Out of sight, out of mind" is not an option. Prior to harvesting, tree care is elementary.

- ▶ natureschutzzentrum-mk.de/download/Pflanzanleitung.pdf
- ▶ natureschutzfonds.de/natur-schuetzen/projektfoerderung

Determining the planting site

Finding a planting site isn't easy. However, it is worth to approach cities (parks department), allotments, companies and other possible land owners as well as relevant initiatives. Dialogue is key, as they offer surprising opportunities, such as finding participants for the event.

In addition to bureaucratic issues, the site must meet the requirements of the planned trees. A standard fruit tree ideally needs an area of ten times ten meters, thus one hundred square meters. Beneficial to the growth of tree, flowers and eventually fruit, is a

sunny spot with soil that's rich in humus. In cities like Berlin, breaking ground you will probably come across road metal and débris from World War II. In cases like this you should at first dispose of things like glass, big rocks and plastic and afterwards nourish the soil with topsoil.

Deciding on what varieties of fruit to choose, it is important to bear in mind the difference between cross-pollinated and self-pollinated varieties.

	standard	semi dwarf	dwarf
crowning	1.60 m up to 1.80 m	1.20 m up to 1.60 m	0.60 m up to 1.20 m
final height	6 m up to 8 m	4 m up 6 m	3 m up to 3.50 m
advantages	provides shade reaches old age	great harvest	early & great harvest easier care & harvest
disadvantages	height complicates tree care & harvest later harvest	height complicates tree care & harvest later harvest	reach young age

Therefore certain varieties have to stand together. It is also recommended to plant more than one fruit tree if it would be the first one in this area. If you are uncertain regarding the combination of suitable trees, ask a tree nursery for help. You can also have a look at the [fruit data bank](#) by the association BUND Lemgo or other websites alike. Tree nurseries don't have every single variety of fruit tree in stock at any time - keep that in mind. Speaking of varieties: try to plant old varieties! Those are more robust, a major cultural asset and better suited for persons suffering from [fruit allergies](#).

► obstsortendatenbank.de

► mundraub.org/blog/alte-afelsorten-allergiker-braeburn

Materials and tools

We already did indicate to acquire the trees from a tree nursery. Be aware of potential delivery costs if it's not possible for you to pick them up yourself and bring them to the planting site. Ideally they sell stakes as well as tree guards to protect the tree against voles and field mice (wire mesh cylinder).

Usually the trees got their first pruning by the tree nursery. If not, you'll need a person with pruning expertise, i.e. a fruit tree expert. If the trees will be delivered directly to the planting site, you should make sure for them to be there at least half an hour before the official start of the planting event. That way, you have some extra time in case of traffic jams etc.

If you or any partners wish to have tree plaques, they need to be prepared. Are they simply laminated or should they be more durable, i.e. made out of acrylic? Pay attention to your finances as well as to agreements with (financial) sponsors and supporters. They maybe would like to be mentioned on the plaque or even have to be according to the agreement. If necessary, prepare some nice certificates for the tree sponsors, thus they can literally hold the responsibility for "their" tree in visibly their own hands. You will find a checklist on [page 18](#). Keep in mind: how do trees, tools and material get to the planting site?

Finding a planting team

If you've come this far, you should, if necessary, recruit helpers to plant with you. Maybe you'll already find your first future tree sponsors among them. Possible target groups could be parents, schools or a company's employees. (► [chapters 4.4](#) and [4.5](#)). Think about how many trees you're going to plant and acquire people accordingly. Don't underestimate the digging of the holes, which can be quite exhausting, depending on the soil conditions. Keep in mind that the planting should be over before sunset.

All participants should be informed about date, time and adequate (weatherproof) clothing, in time. It can be useful if the participants know about the key points of planting a tree, in advance. Therefore, you can provide them with links, tips or relevant literature. To make this process a little easier, you can create a group on mundraub.org. All participants can subscribe to this group, get all the information necessary and exchange their views.

Method

Prepare the planting site before the arrival of all participants. Mark all spots, where a tree is supposed to be planted with a stick or big stone and have the material (tree, tree guard, stake) ready at every spot. After welcoming everyone and introducing the event, you hand out tools and gardening gloves. Let the planting begin.

Exemplary schedule

- be on site for tree delivery
- prepare planting materials
- in case of rain or intense sunshine, set up protection, i.e. pavilion or umbrella
- welcome participants and partners, let them settle in
- distribute name tags (blank) and pens

10 am

- briefing for participants
 - presenting the project
 - get indemnification agreement and photo and video consent agreement signed
 - give advice on the treatment of trees
 - construct the tree guard
- planting including breaks
- attach the tree plaques

12 am

- final check-in
 - thanking everyone
 - explaining further process of follow-up activities (mundraub group, watering, tree care etc.)
 - allow time for photo session
 - goodbye
- collect material (also: waste) and get ready for transport

► mein-gartenbuch.de/wuehlmaus-schutz

After the planting

The trees have been planted and all participants are on their way back. Collect all the tools and leave the site as you found it. Be sure that all trees have been watered sufficiently, have been supplied with the correct plaque and are now ready for their new life. Don't forget to add the trees to the mundraub map, depending on the agreement with partners, and refer to the event in the description.

Example: costs to plant five fruit trees

Item	Quantity	€
fruit tree	5	200.00
stake	5	17.50
wire for tree guard	5	15.00
coconut rope (roll)	1	2.50
staples (bag)	1	3.50
plaques (laminated)	5	3.00
cable ties (bag)	1	7.00
top soil (40 litres a bag)	5	15.00
bark mulch (40 litres a bag)	3	30.00

Spades, shovels, pruners, sledgehammer, ladder, water cans, gloves and wheelbarrow can be at hand or rent. If not at hand, would it be worth it to purchase one or two missing items in regard to future events?

Checklist fruit tree planting

planting material

- stake (1 to 4 per tree, depending on planting site)
- spades, shovels
- wheelbarrow
- pruners, if first pruning hasn't been done yet by the tree nursery
- coconut rope to tie tree to stake, scissors
- staples and hammer (to secure coconut rope on stake)
- sledge hammer
- ladder
- wire for tree guard (non-galvanised) and wire cutter
- gloves
- water cans, filled, if necessary
- top soil
- bark mulch
- plaques including material to attach them

Organisation box

- folder for photo and indemnification agreement
- blank labels for name tags
- paper, pens
- certificates for tree sponsors
- contact list (tree nursery, land owner)
- first-aid kit, in addition: desinfectant, antihistamine for persons allergic to bee and wasp stings, tweezers, tick tweezers
- trash bags
- camera
- pavilion

Other

- _____

4.2 Harvesting event

Preparation and organisation

Planning, executing and post-processing a harvesting event implies a considerable amount of time. First question: why do you want to do a harvesting event?

Do you have too many fruit trees in your garden, do you want to organise a team event (▶ [Kapitel 4.5](#)) or did someone provide their orchard? Do you want to produce juice for friends or your organisation? Take your time to prepare and organise, to set dates with service providers, to coordinate the participants and to clarify the responsibilities for individual tasks.

Harvesting location

You've got your eye set on a certain site or some trees? Or are you still looking to find trees for a harvesting event? Go to the [mundraub map](#), there you'll find public orchards and publicly available fruit trees nearby. It is essential to always clarify the ownership of site and, of course, trees!

▶ mundraub.org/map

Infrastructure

We recommend a one-day-event. More than one day is possible, but this may ask for an accommodation (i.e. in a tent). In any case, it makes sense to set up a "campground" to cook, sit, eat and discuss. A pavilion provides protection against sun and rain, beer benches camp chairs or picnic blankets are perfect seating opportunities. For bigger events you should arrange for a portable toilet. There should be enough water, i.e. in cans (20 or 30 litres) from the local hardware store. We strongly recommend to mow the lawn a few days or weeks before the harvesting event. The harvesting will be easier if the orchard, for instance, is being used as a sheep pasture.

Timing

On the one hand, the right time for the event depends on the people you want to harvest with (i.e. taking in account holidays regarding students). On the other hand, it depends on which fruit you want to harvest. The ideal time to harvest is, of course, when fruit are ripe. A good time to harvest apples and pears is mid September to end October, cherries are primarily ripe in June and July, plums in August and September. Mind the variety, regionale differences and the annual weather dynamics. In our [mundraub harvesting calendar \(► Kapitel 7.4\)](#) you'll find a good overview.

► mundraub.org/blog/wann-äpfel-reif

Harvest

You'll need ladders, storing facilities (i.e. bags, boxes) and if necessary, wheelbarrows. For a bigger harvest you should order a container that can be picked up when filled, and transported to a nearby cidery. Caution: the container must be licensed to transport food!

Furthermore, there should be canvases to put under apple trees, for example. Thus, when shaking the tree, most of the fruit fall on the canvas and are then easier to collect. You can use special poles or hooks to gently rock single branches. For dessert fruit that should

be more durable and therefore should not fall to the ground, you can use fruit pickers with telescopic poles.

What to do with the harvest

Do you want to produce juice or pick dessert fruit? One influencing factor is the fruitfulness of the harvest. The so-called crop estimate has to be done prior to harvest. Thus, you get a picture of how many persons you will need and if a hand press (to rent at [Grüne Liga](#), [NABU](#), [BUND](#) or cideries) will suffice or if you have to allow extra time for the transport to the next cidery. You can also book a mobile fruit press, but be sure to do this at an early stage. Besides, they would need access to water and high voltage current.

As a rule of thumb, you can assume that in a good year, a standard tree in the production stage bears up to one hundred kilogramme of fruit on average. Count the trees and make an estimate. One kilogramme of apples is equivalent to 0.7 litres of juice. That way, you can estimate the finale quantity of juice (► [Seite 23](#)). The ripeness of the fruit is important, too. Is there already a lot of windfall, apples and pears shouldn't be stored as they tend to mould faster. It is then recommended to process the fruit. If you want to press juice on-site, it's best to inform the participants to bring along some empty bottles.

- nabu.de
- bund.net
- grueneliga.de
- mundraub.org/mostereien

Finding a harvesting team

With whom and for whom is the harvesting event? Is it friends, people you would like to bring together or do you organise the event in line with your initiative or another company? That way, you can determine if you talk to people in a personal or more formal way. If applicable, use organisational tools offered in the web. Check the accessibility of the orchard. Is it possible to reach it by public transport and bike or does it require a car? A transport for the participants could be sensible and should be organised in advance. Talk to local communities, create an **event** on mundraub.org use newsletters, i.e. **NABU**, local **BUND** groups, lokale press or social media. Inform the participants to be prepared in case of bad weather. Try to estimate the number of participants. Furthermore you should provide them with all the details of the event: place, if there are toilets and food, what to bring (dishes, gloves, rubber boots, sleeping bag etc.).

» mundraub.org/community/events

» nabu.de

» bund.net

Catering

Easy to prepare are precooked soups or bread with tasty spreads and cheese. It would also be nice if you and other participants would bring salads or you prepare some on the spot and use fruit from the orchard (i.e. for a beet and apple salad). A home-baked cake

and drinks like water, tea or coffee, if a camping stove is available, boost every event's feel-good-factor. Think about how to finance a catering. Some possibilities are donation boxes or a defined contribution per participant.

Method

The day of the event has arrive. We hope for good weather and good energy in the group. As the participants arrive, welcome them, have a coffee or tea and go through the schedule. A possible time to start the harvesting event would be at ten am. Thus, you have enough time for all the preparations on site. Keep in mind to plan an autumn event according to the automn sun. Clarify the responsabilites for the event and build teams for logistics, harvest, catering and kitchen.

Exemplary schedule

- prepare site and event (cooking zone, set up juice press)
- prepare harvesting tools
- be on site for the delivery of the toilet and the container in which the apples will be transported
- pick up the harvesting team, empfangen und ankommen lassen

10 am

- welcoming the participants
 - presenting project and the event's goal
 - make schedule (lunch break, other breaks) and hang it so everyone can see it
 - get indemnification agreement and photo and video consent agreement signed
 - give advice on the treatment of trees and fruit quality: no mouldy apples should be used for juice as it can affect the whole load

12 am

- lunch break
 - allow extra time for food preparation

1 pm

- harvest and if applicable, juice pressing on site and bottling, filling the container with apples

4 pm

- check-in with all participants
 - thanking everyone explaining further process of follow-up activities (who gets juice? When will it be picked up?)
 - goodbye
- collect material (also: waste), pick up of container and portable toilet
- return

After the harvest

In case you have a container that now have to be transported to the cidery, arrange a good time for the pick up, so you're still on site. If you do the transport yourself by car or with a trailer, be sure to secure the boxes. Also, even filled with apples, the boxes should be portable. Pick up or delivery of the pressed juice should be arranged with the cidery. Take care of payment matters, too.

Take down tents, pavilions and mobile kitchen and pick up wast. Portable toilets should get picked up by the company responsible. Make sure,they have access to the site.

If a tree as been damaged, talk to the land owner. Do you think the trees could do with some **pruning**? Talk to the owner about tree care measures in winter. Was it a relatively low apple harvest and is it possibly due to low pollination? There maybe are some nearby beekeepers, that want to set up some beehives in the area come springtime. Could there even be some space for one or two more trees? Talk to the land owner and get information about **tree planting**. (► [chapter 4.1](#)).

Use social media and blogs to tell your followers and readers about the event. Write a thank you e-mail and share experiences and **pictures** (► [chapter 7.6](#)) with people that couldn't be there. Presumably, you have to take care of accounting and logistics (i.e. Where does the juice go?

► mundraub.org/blog/wann-baumschnitt-obstbäume

Checklist harvesting event

Harvesting material

- tape
- ladders
- bags (don't forget some rope to close them!), boxes, bins, wheelbarrows
- gloves
- canvas for windfall
- harvesting poles and hooks
- manual fruit press

Kitchen material and infrastructure

- gas cooker, filled gas container
- catering: food/snacks and drinks
- sharp knives, cutlery, bowls, cups, cutting boards
- to do the dishes: tub, towels
- beer benches and table, camping chairs, picnic blankets
- pavillon or party tent
- water cans
- tent, sleeping bag, camping mat
- trash bags

Organisation box

- folder for receipts and blanks (photo and indemnification agreement, blank labels for name tags)
- paper, pens
- contact list (toilet, container, land owner)
- first-aid kit, in addition: desinfectant, antihistamine for persons allergic to bee and wasp stings, tweezers, tick tweezers

Other

- _____

4.3 mundraub tour

Preparation and organisation

Via the [mundraub map](https://mundraub.org/map) you can easily plan a route. It is important to try this route beforehand to visit the harvesting spots and estimate the duration of the tour. If you are new to the neighborhood or district, it might be even more useful. On average, a tour should take approximately two hours. This also depends on how the tour is done - by foot or by bike. Keep in mind that you may pause at some spots a little longer. If you plan on having a picnic, allow for it to take some time. Are you offering the tour for free? Will you take donations? Or do the participants pay a certain fee. Will there be discounts or group discounts?

► mundraub.org/map

Timing

Technically, you can organise a mundraub tour throughout the whole year, depending on the weather conditions as well as the harvesting calendar. Thus you already have a name for your tour, such as autumn tour, berry tour.

Finding participants

Every mundraub tour can be created as an event on mundraub.org to acquire participants. By creating this **event** every user within 50 kilometers that put their location in their profile will be informed about this event. If there are regular tours, your city can be added to the [mundraub tours website](https://mundraub.org). From there we link to all recent mundraub tour events. In the event you can give a short overview including information about meeting point, beginning, duration, tour by foot or by bike, topic, cost, mobile number and whatever you want to inform your prospective participants about. Use existing networks and social media to attract attention on the event. Whether the tour is by bike or by foot, we recommend a group size of 15 persons at most. Keep in mind that POIs can be located near a sidewalk, that then shouldn't be blocked by the participants.

To make sure that all participating persons show up for the tour, point out that a registration to this event is binding. You can also use an additional registration form, such as Google forms.

A tour for specific groups (children, employees) is possible, too. On this, have a look inside chapters [4.4](#) and [4.5](#).

- ▶ mundraub.org/community/events
- ▶ mundraub.org/mundraub-tour
- ▶ mundraub.org/node/75947

Catering

By preparing the foraged good, you will all have a good opportunity to end the tour on a cozy note. You can prepare a delicious salad out of herbs and edible leaves or flowers. Or you sweeten up the the end of an early summer tour with self made elderflower syrup. Have fun culinary, but think about proper equipment such as picnic blanket, bowls, cutlery or cups.

Prepare a card with the recipe or an offline map with a route of the tour as a giveaway. In the city of Leipzig the first **mundraub bike** (a mobile small kitchen) was constructed to be taken and used on tour.

► mundraub.org/blog/mundraub-mit-mobil

Method

Be at the agreed meeting point at the agreed time or even better, a few minutes earlier. Greet the participants and, if applicable, collect the participant fee. If there are people missing, give them some more minutes to arrive. Give a short overview of the duration and first stops of the tour.

During the tour make sure the group is complete. Especially in urban areas you have to be careful on or at busy roads and crossroads. Stay safe! Conclude the tour with a nice picnic, collect feedback and invite the participants to join the next tour.

Exemplary schedule

After the tour

Try to stay in contact with the participants. Usually people of the mundraub community repeatedly take part in such events. Share your experience in a blog post as well as a special moment on instagram and/or facebook. If you are interested, the blog post could be published on mundraub.org. Therefor just write a mail to info@mundraub.org.

4.4 Orchard day for children

Preparation and organisation

Orchards give space for encounters, common experiences and nature-oriented learning. For an orchard day you will need a good thematic and didactic preparation. At first it's necessary to ascertain the orchard day's target group. Thus it could be an extracurricular field day for students. A field day on school holidays or children's birthday parties are another possibility.

We conceived orchard days for children's groups from first to fourth grade or for children from age six to eleven, respectively and experienced good feedback regarding our modules. An orchard day is going to be a success for the children if there is enough time and space for own discoveries. They should experience the orchard with all their senses, shape it and develop contents in a playful manner. The size of the group plays an important role as well. Thus it makes sense to divide the class in two equal groups as the children tend to be more active and attentive at the same time. The photo and video consent agreement should be signed by the parents before the actual orchard day (via the teachers).

There are different groups of people that can take the initiative to organise an orchard day: school teachers and educators, orchard owners, [fruit plant experts](#).

» [streuobst-paedagogen.de](https://www.streuobst-paedagogen.de)

Event location

For the orchard day you will need a spot with at least one, better more than one, public fruit tree. For a larger group we recommend an orchard with numerous trees. This way, it's easier to assign the children to the respective tasks and discoveries.

Are you still looking for a suitable orchard or fruit trees? Use the [mundraub map](#). You may find public orchards and/or public fruit

trees near you. As always: please make sure, to respect the ownership and, if necessary, speak to the respective owner. They usually are pleasant to talk to and approve if they know the what's going to happen.

► mundraub.org/map

Method

On the following pages we will present you the four different modules we conceived for a day on the orchard.

You have to consider different time periods and the materials, you want to work with. They have to be chosen according to the existing possibilities (such as bee hives for beekeeping, a local beekeeper), the season as well as age and number of children. All modules are going to take about 2,5 hours and can be realised for half a class at best. That way it's possible for two groups at ten children each to do a module simultaneously. They will switch modules after lunch break.

Module 1: Orchard plants

In the centre of this module is the orchard's signification in regard to biodiversity and wildlife habitat for animals and plants.

Module 2: Orchard animals: Wild bees, grasshoppers, earwigs and bugs

The children discover activity and signification of selected species within the orchard habitat (pest and beneficial organism relation, food chain, pollination of flowering plants).

Module 3: Beekeeping on the orchard

The children discover the development from a flower in spring-time to an apple in autumn (or late summer). They get insights into a bee colony, thus learning about life and activities of the honey bee. In doing so they also get an understanding of the honey bee's signification for the orchard as well as the production and composition of honey. In case of no beehives, the practical part could be combined with a discovery of orchard plants (module 1) and animals (module 2).

Module 4: Harvest on the orchard

Children learn about the ripeness of local plums, mirabelles, cherries or apples, how they are harvested and about the possibilities to process them. The harvest good can be eaten fresh or, depending on the fruit, be made into juice with a manual fruit press. This way it can be tasted immediately. If lots of fruit are harvested, several bottles can be filled and taken home as "juicy" souvenirs (► [chapter 4.2](#)). In case of bad weather this module can also be transferred into the classroom, as described in Variation II (► [page 39](#)).

Optional modules

Beyond the modules introduced here, there are of course more possibilities: With children you could also plant trees (► [chapter 4.1](#)) or build insect hotels (► [chapter 4.5](#)) as well as other wild animal shelters.

Conclusion

At the end of every orchard day it would be great to award the children with a certificate, a paper medal or something similar. This way, they can be identified as real orchard experts and have something to proudly show at home.

Module 1: Orchard plants

Period: All year round

Theoretical Part

What grows on trees?

Method Picture puzzle, free story telling, explanations

Workflow Pictures of different fruit are being shown to the children (apple, pear, melon, strawberry, elderflower, currant). Additionally, you have a symbol for trees, bushes and herbaceous plants at hand. Now the children have to assign the fruit to the plant accordingly. In doing so they exchange opinions and experiences regarding this topic. Afterwards, the fruit can also be assigned to their specific seasons or months, respectively.

Practical Part

Nature memory

Cloth of about 1 to 2 sq m

The children swarm out to collect one or two things you can find on an orchard. Those can be known or unknown things. After coming together, all the little explorer's things will be spread out on the cloth and talked about together. Now, one or two children will leave the group for a short moment. During this time, the others will change up to five objects on the cloth (for instance putting them in another position or take them off the cloth completely). The returning children have to find the differences.

Modul 2: Orchard animals - wild bees, earwigs, bugs

Period: End of April until end of September

Theoretical Part

Discovering the world of insects alone

Method Magnifying glass cup or butterfly net

Workflow Every child gets a magnifying glass cup or a butterfly net and, alone or together with other classmates, carefully looks for insects flying and crawling on the orchard. After about ten to fifteen minutes, all come together to present and observe the found insects. During this time, the children should delve deeper into the places the insects were found (on a tree, on a blade of grass, on the ground) and what they were doing in the moment of discovery (feeding, hiding, breeding etc.).

Practical Part

Construction of nesting aids for earwigs

Clay flower pot, acrylic paint, straw, mesh material (e.g. net from onions), cord

Every child paints a clay flower pot. As soon as it's dry, a cord is led through top down through the hole. Make a loop and bind some straw into it. Put a net or some mesh over the pot and knot it firmly with the cord above the pot. Be careful to leave some cord for the hanging.

Modul 3: Bee keeping on the orchard

Period: Mid April until beginning of August

Theoretical Part

Get to know the honey bee

Method Observing a bee colony together with a beekeeper

Workflow The children get a beekeeping veil and, together with the bee keeper, open one of the bee colonies. The bee is introduced as individual and part of a beehive: life cycle, function sharing, reproduction. In the process, the importance of collecting nectar and pollen for the food production is made clear as well as the production of honey and the bee's value for human beings in general. To end the module on a sweet note, there will be a tasting of the self slinged honey.

Practical Part

Sowing: wild flowers, creation: seedbombs

Förderung of flower and species diversity
material: seeds, clay, soil, bowl, water

For an orchard there are special seed mixes to help insects. It is also possible to collect and use seeds of different regional wild plants. Clay and clay powder can be purchased in a pharmacy. It will be easy for the children to find soil on the orchard. Mix about one teaspoon of seeds, four tablespoons of soil and four tablespoons of clay with water until the consistency is smooth but firm. Form small pellets and let them dry. Now the seedbombs are ready to be thrown anywhere as desired.

*Module 4: Harvest on the orchard**Period: Depending on fruit and changing of seasons;**Variation II is in the classroom and thus possible all-year-round***Theoretical Part****I) How is apple juice made?**

Method Preparing pictures of the different stages of pressing apple juice

Workflow The group thinks about different drinks consisting of fruit and how they are made. What are fruity drinks made off and how much fruit is really in them? With the help of pictures the group puts the different stages of juice production in the right order. In doing this, they learn about the process of making apple juice. The ingredients of apples as well as apple juice will be presented as part of a healthy nutrition. The group will be introduced into the following practical part of harvesting and processing the fruit.

Practical Part**I) Children pressing their own juice**

Manual fruit press, providing bottles and canisters for the juice

After the harvest (shaking the trees, picking up apples), the group chooses those apples suitable for juice. Of importance are the fruit's quality and therefore also its resistance. The children wash the chosen fruit and give them into the fruit press (if necessary, cut into quarters beforehand). There, the apples will be shredded and pressed manually. The result is pure and fresh apple juice. Collected in a big canister, the juice is ready to be filled in bottles. As there is no heating involved, the juice shouldn't be kept too long.

Theoretical Part

II) Variety and biodiversity

Method Bringing different varieties of apples

Workflow The group has to describe different varieties of apples that are presented to them. The apples will then be sliced and tasted. Which variety is best suited to which manner of processing? This part can also be done as preparation beforehand in the classroom. Example: All children could bring an apple and write down its name and origin. By doing this, it is shown how apples are harvested everywhere in the world and are transported to Germany, too. Following this exercise, the teacher tell the group about the local apple diversity.

Practical Part

II) Making apple juice

Manual fruit press, cups, providing bottles and canisters for the juice

The brought apples will be cut and pressed into juice with the help of the manual fruit press. The group gets cups and tastes the fresh pressed juice. A bought juice from the supermarket can be tasted in comparison. The children then describe the differences between self-made and bought apple juice.

Exemplary schedule

9 am

- preparation of the orchard: getting the necessary things for the respective event ready (e.g. beekeeper utensils, beekeeping veils for the children)

9.30 am

- get the group and let them settle in
- talk to the teachers about
 - breaks
 - signed photo and video consent agreement
- welcoming the group
- introduction, present daily routine
- give advice on the treatment of trees, plants and animals on the orchard
- divide class into two groups

11.30 am

- group 1: Getting to know the orchard (see Module 1)
- group 2: The honey bee, production of honey (see Module 3)

12 pm

- lunch break (picnic)

2 pm

- group 1: the honey bee, production of honey (see Module 3)
- group 2: getting to know the orchard (see Module 1)

- check-in
 - thanking everyone, handing out certificates
 - clarify further process of follow-up activities with the teachers
- clean up
- return home

After the orchard day

For extracurricular activities schools can use, for instance, field days. Or day-care could develop a special activity for holiday season. For the children, preparation and follow-up activities with regard to content would be desirable. A long-term engagement covering several modules and the orchard's seasonal development is another possibility. For the children, this facilitates their identification with a place as well as actively shaping a part of nature.

Designing posters or creating a folder with reports, experiences and pictures not only is a nice way of remembering the field days but also makes a good foundation to further observe the orchard's development. Share your experiences in the school magazine, write an article on the school's website or a blog post that can be published on mundraub.org (e-mail to info@mundraub.org).

Checklist orchard day

Material according to the event (see columns "Practical part") as well as number of children; für eine Pflanzung oder Ernte-Aktion siehe [chapter 4.1](#) und [chapter 4.2](#)

- paper, pens
- craft materials
- table, picnic blanket, cloth
- educational materials

Organisation box

- certificates
- first-aid kit, in addition: desinfectant, antihistamine for persons allergic to bee and wasp stings, tick tweezer
- trash bags

Other

- _____

4.5 Team event for adults

Preparation and organisation

Companies and administrations regularly offer team events and outings to their employees, that should be well prepared and planned with regard to content. To organise a team event on an orchard is a good opportunity, to experience nature, to create something as a team and to learn something new. We recommend a professional [fruit plant expert](#) for support.

You have to ask yourself, how big the group will be and the amount of time you can schedule for the event. It makes sense to have groups of five to ten persons for about eight hours - which equates one workday. Travel to and from the event should follow the employer's requirements in terms of time and insurance coverage.

► streuobst-paedagogen.de

Event location

For a team event you will need an spot with at least one, better more than one, public fruit tree. For a larger group we recommend an orchard with numerous trees. Are you still looking for a suitable orchard or fruit trees? Use the [mundraub map](#). You may find public orchards and/or public fruit trees near you and are able to plan respective travel times by different means of transport. In any case, it is essential to respect the ownership and, if necessary, get their permission.

According to section 13 and 15 of the [Federal Nature Conservation Act](#), some companies already have planted orchards in the context of their offset activities. They have to compensate for building activities and other environmental interventions. Ask lokal companies, if they have such orchards and, if so, are willing to let them be used for the event (a good example is the "Explorer's

orchard" of the company 50Hertz).

▶ mundraub.org/map

▶ bmu.de/fileadmin/Daten_BMU/Download_PDF/Naturschutz/bnatschg_en_bf.pdf

▶ mundraub.org/50hertz

Infrastructure

It makes sense to set up a "campground" with chairs or beer benches to eat (cook), sit and discuss. Offer drinks, such as tea, coffee and water as well as lunch and little snacks.

Timing

A team event on an orchard can be done in every season - if everyone is dressed accordingly. The following paragraphs not only describe the modules, but also the season or seasons respectively, in which they should be done.

Method

For a team event you can do almost all events or modules described in previous chapters. With a bigger group you could plant several fruit trees or bushes (▶ [Kapitel 4.1](#)). In the summertime, a nice alternative to a usual day in the office could be a harvesting event, a juice tasting included (▶ [Kapitel 4.2](#)) or a visit to the local cidery, a tour included. A day with a beekeeper makes for another great experience (▶ [Kapitel 4.4](#)).

Below, we present you two modules that demand the participants' craftsmanship and benefits the conservation of wildlife as well as environmental education.

Module 1: Building an insect hotel

Preliminary considerations: An insect hotel contributes to the protection of local nature and is a hatchery and habitat for insects of all kinds. It brings lots of beneficial organisms onto an orchard or into a garden that serve as natural pest control workers and pollinate the surrounding flowers of fruit trees and other plants.

Insects don't exclusively use insect hotels as insects' hibernation: Bees and cockchafers, for instance, rather use spacious housings like hedges or a house's roof structure.

An insect hotel should be standing near local wild plants and planned as a permanent integral part of the location. Thus, it is necessary to know the area's owner. Ask them if the erection of such an insect hotel would be possible and if there is something that has to be paid attention to regarding the event. Really important for the hotel is a safe and stable position, therefore you should plan an anchoring according to the underground.

Timing: You could build and set up an insect hotel all year round. In winter, insects are going to use it more as a place to hibernate, in summer, to breed and bring up their offspring.

Location: An insect hotel should get direct solar radiation, thus facing south. Protection from the rain is possible but not as important as direct sun radiation. Besides a sufficient supply of flowers nearby as food for the insects, a water supply (watering hole for rainwater, for instance) as well as sand and clay to close the breeding ground.

Duration: How long the construction takes depends on the size of the envisioned insect hotel. Take into account the purchase of material and the hotel's conceptual planning when you time the event. Or you could hand this part over to a [fruit plant expert](#). The construction of the hotel as well as the setting up, including the foundation, could take up to half a day. The filling and fixing of the material takes a little less time.

Material & tools: Because of soil wetness and small animals, the insect hotel should not be standing directly on the ground, but at a height of approximately one meter. A stabile and long-lasting construction of four rectangular blocks of wood and a shelf with different compartments should work as a basic frame. Smaller hotels to hang would be another possibility. You will find further materials and tools in the checklist on [page 51](#). It would be great to use items from the event location and other natural materials. What you have to think about: Who gets the material and tools, how is it financed and who is responsible for its transport?

► streuobst-paedagogen.de

Module 2: Tree pruning

Preliminary considerations: A tree grows without pruning, too. However, it does make sense to prune the tree for it to get a certain shape or for it to recover quicker after storm damages or sicknesses. Furthermore, pruning encourages an increased flowergrowth and with it an increased fruiting. I.e., right pruning fosters a fruit tree's health and life span. Ultimately, it enhances the harvest as well as the fruit quality.

To prune a tree we recommend consulting an expert, for instance, a fruit tree expert. There is a number of information in literature and materials from local environmental organisations, such as **NABU**, **BUND** or **Grüne Liga**. Make sure to clarify the ownership of the tree or trees, respectively.

By pruning a tree right after planting, especially young fruit trees are cut back to one main and three side shoots. This kind of pruning determines the future crown structure and encourages the growth. Pruning fruit trees to control shape and size must be done once a year until the tree has been grown for ten years at one place. This helps to encourage the crown's carrying capacity through the strengthening of the main shoot. Through regenerative pruning the crown will be thinned out and ventet, thus giving the tree fresh energy.

Timing: In general, most trees need one **pruning** per year, tops. Usually this happens between November and February - i.e. winter - by the time the trees shed their leaves, but no new sprouts have been grown yet. However, frost is a no-go.

Duration: How long it takes to prune a tree depends on the height of the tree, or trees respectively, the kind of pruning you have planned and the number of people that participate.

▶ nabu.de

▶ bund.net

▶ grueneliga.de

▶ mundraub.org/blog/wann-baumschnitt-obstbaeume

Module 3: Benjes hedge

Preliminary considerations: A Benjes hedge is, as the name suggests, a hedge that provides habitat and shelter for birds, insects as well as small mammals. It also serves as a windbreak. Have you been pruning your trees? Great! Use the twigs and branches you cut from bushes and trees to build a hedge that is about four meters long and one meter high. This hedge releases nutrients through self decomposition and encourages new plants to grow. Over time, those will replace the original hedge.

The hedge should be secured using stakes or planted bushes spaced at intervals of about one meter. This way, you don't have to worry about the question of where to dispose of the pruning "waste".

Timing: You should build a Benjes hedge when you prune or trim your lawn, your bushes or trees. Bushes and trees should not be pruned during vegetation periods or during the breeding season of birds (March 1 until September 15).

Duration: Depending on the collected material and the envisioned size of the hedge, you need to schedule enough time to set up the stakes or bushes as anchoridge.

The Benjes hedge is a project, that develops and grows over a longer period of time.

Exemplary schedule

▼	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • preparation of the respective event • get tools and materials ready • receive the participants and let them settle in
9 am	_____
▲	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • welcoming the group • introduction, present daily routine • arrange breaks, other arrangements • give advice on the treatment of trees, plants and animals on the orchard
9.30 am	_____
▼	<p>Ex. Module 1: Insektenhotel</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • short introduction into the significance and function of an insect hotel • divide group into two: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ prepare fundament ◦ building the frame and anchoridge ◦ prepare filling: inspecting the materials in the vicinity, work on prepared materials to fit the frame
11.30 am	_____
▲	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • lunch break (picnic)
12.30 pm	_____
▼	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • set up the frame and anchoridge • put filling material in the frame/frame compartments
2.30 pm	_____
▲	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • break
3 pm	_____
▼	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • check-in <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ group photo ◦ collecting impressions, feedback ◦ thanking everyone, clarify further process of follow-up activities ◦ clean up ◦ return home

After the team event

To organise a team event on an orchard with one of the modules outlined above or another activity out of this handbook, is a great opportunity to observe the development of an orchard over a longer period of time. For example, after pruning or building a Benjes hedge in one year, it will be exciting to experience an increase of harvest the following year. If applicable, a longer connection between a company or a group with an orchard and its owner.

It's nice to record all the experiences by taking photos or making a short video (► [chapter 7.6](#)). Write about the event and publish the post on the company website, your own blog or possibly mundraub.org (e-mail to info@mundraub.org).

Checklist team event

Material: insect hotel

- hammer-in ground sockets (for anchoring)
- hammering tools, screw driver, saw, sand paper, sanding block, spade
- rectangular stakes, shelves
- clay
- screws
- roofing paper, bitumen, nails
- concrete, sand, water
- filling materials: straw, pre-drilled log wood, fir cones, small bamboo canes, plant stems, wood wool, deadwood, sand, clay, hollow bricks, twigs

Material: Benjes hedge

- pruning shears
- stakes, spade
- bushes, twigs
- hand saw

Tools: pruning

- pruning shears
- hand saw
- ladder

Organisation box

- folder for receipts and blanks (photo and indemnification agreement)
- first-aid kit, in addition: desinfectant, antihistamine for persons allergic to bee and wasp stings, tweezers, tick tweezers
- gloves

Other

- _____

5. Make your ideas visible

The edible city is digital, too. To inspire people to participate, talk about it, invite them to events, show photos and network. Our services and the [mundraub](#) community will help you to make your ideas and events visible and to attract followers.

Creating events on [mundraub.org](#)

There are over 70,000 registered users on [mundraub.org](#). A part of them can be found on the [mundraub map](#) as they have put their location in their profile. By adding a planting or harvesting [event](#) or a bicycle tour and providing time and place, you will reach all those registered users in the vicinity as they automatically receive an e-mail. Of course, the [mundraub](#) team will post your event on social media if you want to, thus generating more attention.

Founding groups on [mundraub.org](#)

Groups are an opportunity to discuss and meet with other fruit and nature enthusiasts in your vicinity. To search for a group in your city or area, go to the [mundraub.org group website](#) and put the desired location in the address search field. If there are no results, look for the violet group icon on the [mundraub map](#). If there are no groups in your area, yet, found one and invite your friends to participate. As with the events, by creating a new group all registered users, that put their location in their profile and are in the vicinity of the group are automatically notified. If interested, they can join your group.

- ▶ mundraub.org/map
- ▶ mundraub.org/community/events
- ▶ mundraub.org/community/groups

Embedding the edible landscape in your website

The [mundraub map](https://mundraub.org/map) maps places where you can find fruit trees and bushes, herbs as well as events, groups and cideries. With the [mundraub](https://mundraub.org/map) iframe you are now able to embed a detail of your choice of the [mundraub map](https://mundraub.org/map) in your website. By doing so, you can visualise your personal edible city, area or district. Thus, you share the fruits of your city, events and at the same time, you spread the [mundraub](https://mundraub.org/map) philosophy. Using a common digital language, the awareness of edible landscapes is being raised across city limits. To embed the map via iframe, go to the [mundraub map](https://mundraub.org/map), click on "Karte einbetten" (embed map) and follow the instructions.

- ▶ mundraub.org/map

Visibility via importing fruity tree inventories

Some cities or municipalities administrate a so-called tree inventory. In it, all city trees are being listed according to species, year, position and other individual criteria. This way, departments of parks and gardens always have a recent overview of their city's tree population. mundraub offers a service for municipalities to add their fruit trees to the [mundraub map](#) and, thus, make them visible for their citizens. In addition, we import the cities' existing tree inventories into the [mundraub map](#). We are happy to give you more details regarding this cooperation (e-mail to info@mundraub.org). Of course, the municipalities can visualise their fruit trees on their website via the mundraub iframe.

► mundraub.org/map

Do good and talk about it

Did you creat an event, found a group or have an idea for a mundraub tour, harvesting or planting event? Tell people about it, write a blog post for your website or send your text to info@mundraub.org. You are parte of an organisation that sends newsletters or press report? Great! Share it with the world - ideally with photos. You have an [Instagram account](#)? Share some nice photos and tell stories. Sharing is caring: Think about protecting the rights of others before spreading photos etc. If you use pictures, make sure to know the copyright of the picture's owner (ideally yourself) as well as the pictured person or persons, respectively (►[chapter 7.6](#)).

► instagram.com/mundraub_org

6. Implementing the edible city

muntraub supports the development of edible landscapes by connecting different people, municipalities, regions and districts with the help of fruit, herbs and nuts. Furthermore, muntraub.org serves as a digital networking platform to mobilise people, pass knowledge and spread the idea of edible cities and landscapes as a new reality and future.

To add to our digital tools, muntraub wrote two **books** about the edible city as well as the maintenance of edible landscapes.

With this (transfer) handbook we're taking a step further by sharing our practical muntraub knowledge promoting edible cities with people that encourage and share our idea.

We aim to gather and expand practical knowledge on muntraub tours, at harvesting or planting events and orchard days.

► muntraub.org/unsere-buecher

mun draub connects

Edible cities develop in different and creative ways. Whether as “grassroot movement” initiated by citizens or the local transition initiative, as is the case in the city of Kassel, or initiated and developed on the part of local authorities, as is the case in the city of Andernach. The idea to encourage and establish edible cities is constantly growing further. Municipalities see the added value for themselves and for whole regions, if people engage in a project and connect and share ideas beyond city limits. To reach agreements in terms of urban planning, that are applicable nationwide is one of the big challenges (cf. Russo et al. 2017).

With this handbook, mun draub aims to support municipalities as well as citizens in conceiving and implementing edible cityscapes and to accompany them on their way to an *Edible City*.

We connect fruity green with surrounding neighbourhoods and initiate individual forms of participation.

7. Good to know

7.1 mundraub rules

A forager (as part of the mundraub community)...

... keeps their hands off the fruit if there is any doubt about the ownership of a tree or bush.

... is careful with trees, the surrounding nature and the animals that live there.

... shares the fruits of their discovery. Picking for one's own need is okay, commercial foraging needs an official license.

... is happy to give back to edible landscapes. Whether it is with a good conversation about our precious fruit or even by engaging in the care or planting of fruit trees.

7.2 Law and order

mundraub for everyone or criminal fruit theft?

Since the reform of the criminal law in 1975, the so-called "Mundraub" (i.e. food theft) ceased to exist as separate crime. Although this crime has been removed from the present German criminal code, "Mundraub" still is prohibited and can be prosecuted. In lieu of the "Mundraub" section is now section 242 (1):

„Whosoever takes chattels belonging to another away from another with the intention of unlawfully appropriating them for himself or a third person shall be liable to imprisonment not exceeding five years or a fine”

Yes, already the "attempt shall be punishable" (section 242 (2)). Thus, sneaking a handful of cherries without permission is legally the same as, for instance, stealing five euro from another person's wallet. According to section 248a:

"Theft and unlawful appropriation of property of minor value may only be prosecuted upon request in cases under section 242 and section 246, unless the prosecuting authority considers proprio motu that prosecution is required because of special public interest."

Thus, police or prosecution will only get involved if, for instance, the fruit tree's owner files a complaint. Nevertheless, without explicit permission "Mundraub" is theft and can be punished as such. To make sure, our community is on the safe side snacking delicious fruit, they have to ascertain the ownership of the fruit tree or bush or,

respectively, the land these are standing on. A judge will not accept the argument, one relied on an internet platform - according to a **legal expert**.

► arag.de/service/infos-und-news/rechtstipps-und-gerichtsurteile/sonstige/4527/

Who does this apple tree belong to?

There are no such things as ownerless trees in Germany. Even if there is no fence and the trees are full of ripe fruit that apparently no one is harvesting, trees and fruit belong to the respective land owner.

In Germany, trespassing on private property can have legal consequences, so open your eyes and ears when foraging! An owner can be an individual or - in case of many trees on the side of the road, in parks or in other public places - a municipality, the federal state or the federal government.

Having a personal conversation with the owner is the best and sometimes only way to find out if they would allow the tree to be harvested. You could even offer tree care measures.

Of course, it sometimes takes some courage to make the first step, some perseverance to make your intention clear and, finally, some investigative skills to find out who the tree belongs to. After a first conversation between owner and forager, many interesting things can develop: some lovely anecdotes as well as creative solutions on how to raise awareness for trees that are not harvested and how they can become a common for us all again.

Fruit trees on the **side of public streets and roads** usually belong to the respective municipality, rural district, federal states or the federal government. Of course, one could argue that those trees are standing on public land and therefore they are or were financed by the taxpayer. In some areas and initiated by, for instance, NGOs

cideries or municipalities, individuals adopt public trees and, thus, become their godparents. They provide professional care for the fruit trees (by themselves or experts) and are free to harvest the fruit after.

Parks and public places are subject to similar conditions as public streets and roads. Some municipalities officially

release their tree inventory, others prohibit the use of public fruit trees. Usually, those kinds of prohibitions are no malicious acts on the part of city administrations. They rather fear damages to the trees through improper harvesting. Or worse, a forager could hurt themselves severely by, for instance, climbing a tree.

As is the case for every tree: At first you have to be sure about the ownership, then you are allowed to forage. The responsible contact person in municipalities is the mayor or the local representative. At rural district level the respective rural district office can provide information, for bigger cities the department of parks and gardens at town or district level would be responsible.

And what about the fruit on an **overhanging branch or twig that outreaches the garden fence** from one property to another or, respectively, to the public sidewalk? According to the German Civil Code, section 911:

"Fruit that falls from a tree or a bush onto a neighbouring plot of land is deemed to be the fruit of this plot of land. This provision does not apply if the neighbouring plot of land is for public use."

Thus, fruit still hanging on the branch, belongs to the respective garden owner. Naturally, to help along by shaking the tree is not permitted.

You frequently pass a private garden where a fruit tree is still standing without being harvested? Pluck up the courage and leave a personal message or ring the doorbell. The owner often share their fruit, being happy it actually is used.

With **bigger outdoor areas**, such as meadows, fields, and acres, there usually is a land owner, too. Here it is important to know, that often public as well as private areas in the countryside must not be fenced. Even an orchard open to the public must not be trespassed. To find a contact person responsible for outdoor areas sometimes proves to be a little bit more complicated. If you're fortunate enough you will meet somebody working in the field, a farmer for instance, and you can address them directly.

Maybe the next village chat could give you an answer regarding the question of land ownership or land management, respectively. In case you can't find a local contact person, try land registry offices, environmental authorities of your respective federal state or agricultural cooperatives. However, you don't have a legal claim to information.

The following regulation according to the **Federal Nature and Conservation Act** section 39 (3) applies to the foraging of berries, herbs and mushrooms in **forests**:

“... anyone may carefully remove from nature and take possession of, at sites not subject to any prohibitions on access, and for their own personal needs, small amounts of wild flowers, grasses, ferns, mosses, lichens, fruits, mushrooms, herbs for tea and medicinal herbs and branches of wild plants.”

In nature reserves - whether forest or meadow - foraging or harvesting is generally prohibited.

► bmu.de/fileadmin/Daten_BMU/Download_PDF/Naturschutz/bnatschg_en_bf

Safety, accident & liability

To look after your own safety as well as the safety of all participants and passersby should have top priority. Always check the structural safety of trees and branches carefully when setting up the ladder. Climbing trees is only advisable if everything else failed: By doing so, not only can a tree's bark get hurt easily, but even thick branches can break faster than you would think. Be especially careful when harvesting old trees or cherry trees which are known to be quite breakable.

Furthermore, it would be painful if a big apple falls from a great height and hits someone's head. Picking apples having a bike helmet on the head seems unusual at first but prevents ugly bruises. If you harvest on the sides of streets and roads, be sure to abide by the rules of road safety. This means, for example, to not interfere with traffic, to not park vehicles on the shoulder and to remove any pollution on the roads immediately (i.e. fallen fruit - don't forget a broom!). Also, wearing safety vests is always a good idea. That way, you will be visible from afar. Especially group activities on busy roads can create serious risks for all participants. In this case, it would be worth to make a formal request to the responsible authority.

They offer preliminary support and, if necessary, know of other bodies responsible.

However, what happens if, on a third-party property, a participant stretches themselves a little too far to reach a particularly tasty-looking apple, falls off the ladder and injures themselves seriously? Does everything happen at their own risk? Will the garden owner be

responsible if something happens as it is their tree a participant is falling out of? As a general rule, harvesting and tree care are "favours", thus, in those cases the casualty is liable for the accident.

At bigger fundraisers harvesting events with numerous participants (e.g. field trips), it is recommended to have an event insurance in case of any accidents - in spite of all carefulness and safety precautions taken. Such insurance can be taken out with any insurance company. Another possibility is an indemnification agreement that

must be signed by all participants and that relieves you from all liability claims as organizer (► [chapter 7.5](#)). You want to take pictures or shoot a videos at an event to have some content for your blog, your website or facebook page? Get the permission of all participants in advance (► [chapter 7.6](#)).

7.3 Harvesting tips

Mirabelle

Ripe mirabelles just fall from the tree: Put a big cloth under the tree and shake the tree carefully. The same actually goes for mulberries. Those even ripe in stages, thus harvesting season can take up to several week.

▶ mundraub.org/blog/mirabellenkuchen

Apple

To harvest apples, it is recommended to bring a long ladder as well as fruit pickers with telescopic poles to reach the fruit. They are suitable for pears or stone fruit, such as plums, too.

▶ mundraub.org/blog/wann-äpfel-reif

Quince

As overripe quinces foul fast, they can be harvested in an early riping stage. Thus, quinces may be stored for up to two months, separate from other fruit.

▶ mundraub.org/blog/wann-sind-quitten-reif

Walnut

Ripe walnuts fall from the tree all by themselves, you don't need to shake the tree or knock off the nuts. Doing this would only damage the tree.

▶ mundraub.org/blog/haselnüsse-walnüsse-gesund

Chestnut

Don't confuse sweet chestnuts with the inedible horse chestnuts. The fruit of the sweet chestnut sits in a shell covered with long soft thorns. The horse chestnut's shell is also covered in thorns, however, those are hard, short and painful.

▶ mundraub.org/blog/maronen-rezepte-ernte

Blackberry

Blackberries should be washed carefully before eating - just as every other fruit. It is especially recommended with wild berries as they may be contaminated by the fox tapeworm.

► mundraub.org/unsere-buecher/stadt-essbar

Elder

In the summertime, elder is an important bee pasture. You can collect the flowers in umbels and use them to make syrup. The same harvesting technique goes for the berries. Use a fork to easily get the berries off the umbel.

► mundraub.org/blog/6-gründe-holunder-gesund

Sea buckthorn

Ripe fruit squash easily and besides, they are surrounded by thorn. Hence, carefully cut the sprout tips holding the berries and put them in the freezer. In a frozen state, the berries can be knocked off gently.

► mundraub.org/blog/verarbeitung-sanddorn-gesund

Blackthorn

Due to the presence of tannins, blackthorn is best to be harvested after the first frost. Or put the fruit for a few days in the freezer so that the level of tannins subsides. They are responsible for the blackthorn's bitter taste.

► mundraub.org/blog/welche-früchte-im-winter

Juniper

Juniper is a conifer, growing as a tree or bush. Therefore, juniper berries actually are cones. The juniper itself is a protected species, however, collecting the berries is permitted. Please keep in mind to only pick the ripe blue berries. The ripening process may take up to three or four years.

► mundraub.org/blog/wacholder-reif-gin

7.4 Harvesting calendar

7.5 Template: Indemnification agreement

Indemnification agreement

Event/date

.....

Organizer

.....
.....
.....

Event location

.....
.....
.....

Declaration

My participation in the above mentioned event is voluntary and at my own risk. I agree to release from liability and to indemnify and hold harmless the organizer, its servants, its agents as well as the property owner.

All my questions have been answered, I'm feeling mentally and physically able to participate in die event.

Date

Participant's name

Signature

.....
.....
.....
.....
.....

7.6 Template: Photo and video consent agreement

Photo and video consent agreement

Event/date

.....

(please check)

I voluntarily agree that any pictures taken and/or videos shot of myself

.....

(Full name)

and/or my daughter/son

.....

(Full name, date of birth)

during the above mentioned event are allowed to be used by the organizer for documentation and public relation purposes only.

.....

Place, date, signature (if applicable, parent or legal guardian)

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